

PROVISION AND REJUVENATION OF LEARNING SUPPORT FACILITIES AT MTs BAITUL MUBAROK, KUBU RAYA REGENCY

Asmadi^{1*}, Sarpawi², Rizal³, Iwan Supardi⁴, Helyanto⁵, Rona Ariyansyah⁶, Muhammad Taufik
Habibillah Ibnu Ahmad⁷, Rasiwan⁸, Muhammad Abduh⁹, Susi Hariyani¹⁰

^{1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10}Department of Civil Engineering, Politeknik Negeri Pontianak

*Corresponding Author: amadipk25@gmail.com

Received : 20 November 2025

Published : 17 January 2026

Revised : 01 December 2025

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.54443/morfai.v6i2.4910>

Accepted : 25 December 2025

Publish Link : <https://radjapublika.com/index.php/MORFAI/article/view/4910>

Abstract

The limited learning facilities at MTs Baitul Mubarak, including the absence of classroom ceilings, damaged doors, and unfit desks, chairs, and whiteboards, have hindered comfort and safety in the learning process. The Community Service Program (PKM) of the Civil Engineering Department at Politeknik Negeri Pontianak was carried out to provide and refurbish these facilities while offering practical learning experiences for students. The method included situation analysis, planning, material preparation, product fabrication in the workshop, and delivery to the partner. The program produced 36 desks, 76 chairs, 3 whiteboards, and 3 sets of classroom doors, all meeting the standards of Permendiknas No. 24/2007. The activity improved the quality of learning facilities, enhanced student comfort, and strengthened students' technical skills and social awareness, although ceiling repairs could not be completed due to budget limitations.

Keywords: *Community Service, Learning Facilities, Refurbishment, Mts Baitul Mubarak.*

INTRODUCTION

Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTs) is a formal educational institution equivalent to the Junior High School (SMP) level and is under the supervision of the Ministry of Religion. The implementation of MTs is based on Government Regulation (PP) No. 55 of 2007, which defines madrasahs as formal educational units under the guidance of the Minister who provides general education with Islamic characteristics, as well as Law (UU) No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System (Sisdiknas), which affirms its position at the level of basic education. The tsanawiyah level, in the learning process, integrates general subjects with Islamic Religious Education as a whole. According to KMA (Decree of the Minister of Religion) No. 184 of 2019 concerning the PAI and Arabic curriculum, the madrasah curriculum and the general provisions section state that, Madrasah Tsanawiyah is a formal education unit that is at the first level of advanced elementary education, with a curriculum structure that combines general subjects and Islamic Religious Education subjects in more depth.

One of the MTs in Indonesia, precisely located at Jalan Perintis Parit Serong, RT. 037/RW. 010, Pal Sembilan Village, Sungai Kakap District, Kubu Raya Regency, West Kalimantan Province, namely Baitul Mubarak. MTs Baitul Mubarak was established by KH. Syahrul Mubaroq, LC on 1 Muharram 1438 H / December 20, 2016 AD, on a land with an area of ± 1,900 m², with the foundation of the spirit of jihad and the deepening of religious education from various circles of the surrounding Muslim community. The Operational Decree (SK) from this madrasah is number 1341 of 2021, which came into effect on April 5, 2021. Information obtained from the Data and Information Technology Center (Pusdatin) of the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education (Kemendikdasmen) in 2025, Madrasah Baitul Mubarak has a private status (under the auspices of the Ministry of Religion) with a National School Identification Number (NPSN) 70027433. The number of students is 84 students with educators and education staff with a total of 22 people, as well as 6 rooms for the teaching and learning process and 3 rooms for students to stay.

Educational facilities are various devices, materials, and equipment that are used directly in teaching and learning activities, such as books, props, tables, chairs, and other learning media (Ministry of National Education, 2004). The current condition of MTs in January 2025, classrooms are still not equipped with ceilings, many doors are damaged, desks and chairs are severely damaged, whiteboards are not suitable for use, and the floors and walls are in very poor condition or have not met feasibility standards. Based on the Regulation of the Minister of National Education Number 24 of 2007, each student has the right to obtain a set of tables and chairs that are used during the

learning process in the classroom. The table and chair must meet certain standards, including being sturdy, stable, and easy to move. In addition, the size and design of the chair, including its seat and backrest, must be comfortable and appropriate to support the student's learning position. The design of the desk also needs to pay attention to comfort, especially enough space for students' feet to move freely under the desk. Another supporting facility is a whiteboard, which must be at least one piece in each classroom, with a size of at least 90 cm x 200 cm, and installed in a position that is easy to see by all students in the classroom. Community Service Activities (PKM) of the Pontianak State Polytechnic (Polnep) with the source of PNBPN Polnep funds in 2025, are used as activities to assist MTs Baitul Mubarak in providing and rejuvenating facilities, facilities and infrastructure to support learning. The process of provision and rejuvenation was carried out at the Civil Engineering Workshop, Department of Civil Engineering, Pontianak State Polytechnic, which involved many student roles, with the direction of Lecturers and Technicians. The benefits obtained are not only for MTs Baitul Mubarak Partners, namely students, student involvement in PKM activities provides various strategic benefits. This activity not only develops soft skills such as communication and collaboration (Wulandari & Prasetyo, 2023), but also hones professional skills and problem-solving through field practice (Sari et al., 2024). In addition, students are more sensitive to social issues so as to foster concern and moral responsibility for society (Hidayat, 2022). PKM also plays a role in shaping professional character and ethics (Nurhayati & Lubis, 2021), improving their adaptability to the field environment (Arifin et al., 2025), and strengthening campus relations with the community as part of the tridharma (Kusumawati, 2020). Not only that, PKM activities also add to students' portfolios and practical experience for future career needs (Dewi & Mahendra, 2024). Judging from this background, the purpose of the Community Service (PKM) activity is to be involved in the role of the PKM team and students of the Department of Civil Engineering of the Pontianak State Polytechnic in the provision and rejuvenation of educational support facilities in the community, especially MTs Baitul Mubarak partners.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Faculty of Civil Engineering

Pontianak State Polytechnic (POLNEP) is a state vocational university in Pontianak City, West Kalimantan, Indonesia, which emphasizes the mastery and development of science and technology to support the industrialization era and produce quality graduates who are ready to compete in the industrial world (Pontianak State Polytechnic, 2025). The members of the PKM Team implementation are 10 people, with 1 chairman and 9 lecturers, from the Department of Civil Engineering (JTS), Pontianak State Polytechnic. Students are also inseparable from the involvement of 8 people from various types of study programs and semesters in the JTS environment. Another important role is also in technicians or instructors as many as 2 people, especially in the Wood Workshop Practice course.

Program PKM

The Community Service Program (PKM) at the Pontianak State Polytechnic (Polnep) is an activity carried out as part of the implementation of the Tri Dharma of Higher Education to transfer knowledge, technology, and skills from the academic community to the community in order to solve real problems and improve the skills and welfare of the community in a sustainable manner (Polnep Research and Community Service Center, 2023). This activity is fully funded by the Polnep Research and Community Service Center in 2025. The program has terms and conditions and procedures that must be met. One of these stages is socialization, administrative selection, reporting (proposals, progress, and finals) within the implementation period in accordance with the predetermined timeline.

MTs Baitul Mubarak Partners

The target of this research activity is called a partner, which in this activity the partner involved is MTs Baitul Mubarak. Madrasah Tsanawiyah Baitul Mubarak is a *Madrasah Tsanawiyah* (junior high school level) with the status of a private school that provides formal education in Sungai Kakap District, Kubu Raya Regency, West Kalimantan Province, Indonesia, with a focus on general and religious learning in accordance with the national curriculum and madrasah education standards (MTs Baitul Mubarak, 2025). The PKM Team's assessment is based on the results of the situation analysis that this school is suitable as an object and partner partner in PKM JTS Polnep activities. Conditions at the time of analysis show that partners can be targeted in the empowerment, rejuvenation, and provision of educational facilities. This is in line with and compatible with the Polnep PKM program and MTs Baitul Mubarak was chosen as the object and partner of the program.

Situation, Condition, and Handling Analysis

The results of the survey stated in the analysis of the situation and conditions found that, the classroom compartment did not have a ceiling, many classrooms, and huts were damaged, many chairs and tables were lacking and the condition was severely damaged, the blackboard in the classroom was not suitable and the floor and walls, all of which had been severely damaged. This condition makes the students lack desks and chairs, damaged whiteboards, so that it is very disruptive in the teaching and learning process. In addition, the safety factor is an important determinant in the learning process, if the facilities are inadequate and can increase safety risks. Based on this, the PKM Team wants to run this program with these partners so that they can minimize unwanted things.

RESEARCH METHODS

PKM activities carried out by the Civil Engineering Department team consisting of lecturers and students, as well as technicians. The partner is MTs Baitul Mubarak, which is located at Jalan Perintis Parit Serong, RT 037, RW 010, Pal IX Village, Sungai Kakap District, Kubu Raya Regency, West Kalimantan Province. Mitra currently has as many as 84 students, with a teaching staff of 12 ustadz and 10 ustadzah. There are 6 classrooms for learning and 3 rooms for students to stay. The process and method in this activity has several stages, namely: Situation Identification and Analysis, Needs Analysis, Activity Preparation, Activity Implementation, and Submission of Activity Products.

Figure 1. Stages of PKM Activities

Situation Identification and Analysis

The stages of identification and analysis of the situation are carried out by visually surveying the condition. The assessment is carried out on the condition of the classroom, namely on the structure and non-structure of the classroom building as well as the learning facilities at the Partner.

Needs Analysis

The needs analysis is carried out after the identification and analysis stages of the situation are completed. The PKM team assessed that MTs Baitul Mubarak partners needed several treatments. The limited fund ceiling provided by the Polnep Research and Community Service Center makes the handling carried out impossible to carry out as a whole. The focus is based on the funds provided, namely in the form of rejuvenation and the provision of educational facilities. The target or product of the PKM activity is the manufacture of 36 units of tables, 76 units of chairs, 3 blackboards, and 3 sets of classroom doors.

Preparation of Activities

The results of the needs analysis that have been taken into account are then carried out in the preparation stage of the activity. Preparation of activities is to make work drawings, and prepare tools and materials. The size for the chair is in accordance with Permendiknas 24/2007 Attachment II (Junior High School / MTs Infrastructure Advice Standard) which is 38-43 cm high, the width and depth of the seat ≤ 40 cm. The table is 65-75 cm high with a \geq length of 60 cm, and a width of 40-50 cm. The whiteboard is planned with a size of 120 x 240 cm with a height from the lower floor of 75-90 cm. While the doors are 3 units, the size follows the one that has been installed with a height of 180-200 cm and a width of 120-150 cm. The specifications for all these materials are that they must be strong, stable, and easy to move, and have a flat surface, not dazzling, and easy to clean.

Implementation of Activities

The next stage when the working drawings are ready in accordance with the applicable guidelines and regulations, is the implementation of activities. The implementation of the activity, namely product making, was carried out at the Workshop of the Department of Civil Engineering by students which was applied to the Wood Workshop Practice course, with the direction of Lecturers and Instructors.

Submission of Activity Results Products

The results of the implementation of activities with the number of products that have been planned, will then be submitted to partners. The handover process is planned after the product is finished. The assumption of time is at the end of August according to the *timeline* of the activity plan. The handover activity will be carried out symbiologically and in a mutual cooperation with partners.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PKM activities are carried out in accordance with the planned stages and result in the provision and rejuvenation of learning facilities at Mita MTs Baitul Mubarak that are suitable for use, so that it can provide comfort in the teaching and learning process, as well as increase safety in the process.

Situation Identification and Analysis Results

Based on the results of surveys and interviews, MTs Baitul Mubarak has inadequate classrooms, one of which is the condition of the ceiling that does not exist, and the door is severely damaged. In addition, learning support facilities in the form of tables, chairs and whiteboards are not suitable conditions, based on applicable standards and guidelines.

Figure 2. Classroom Conditions Without Ceiling

Figure 3. Condition of Doors, Tables, Chairs, and Whiteboards

Implementation and Mobilization Results

The products made at the Civil Engineering Workshop, Department of Civil Engineering, Pontianak State Polytechnic, are in the form of 36 units of desks, 76 units of chairs, 3 whiteboards, and 3 sets of classroom doors. The time required in the implementation of the activity is for 10-12 weeks in the Workshop Work Practice course. All products that have been made are then mobilized at MTs Baitul Mubarak as partners. The size and specifications of the products made have referred to the Minister of National Education Regulation Number 24/2007 Attachment II concerning Standards for Infrastructure Suggestions for Junior High School/MTs.

Figure 4. Product Creation and Mobilization by Students and Lecturers

Product Submission Process

The submission process will be carried out on Saturday, August 30, 2025. The handover activity is carried out symbiologically and placed according to the condition of each product. Tables, chairs, and whiteboards are placed in the classroom, while for doors, installation and replacement of old doors are carried out. During the activity process, it was attended by PKM Team Members and students involved, and witnessed by representatives of partners.

Figure 5. The Process Of Handing Over and Installing PKM Products

The results of the implementation of PKM activities are expected to provide benefits to MTs Baitul Mubarak Partners, especially in learning facilities. Another impact is expected to be on students, which improves *soft skills* in Woodworking Practice courses, and builds social concern for others, especially in the field of education. Real benefits can also be felt by student partners and the surrounding community. For students and educators, it is hoped that it will increase the sense of comfort and security in every learning process activity, with the empowerment of

these facilities will facilitate and increase motivation in learning. The community is also expected to have an impact even if not directly, which increases a positive social impact.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This Community Service activity was carried out by lecturers, technicians, and students within the Department of Civil Engineering, Pontianak State Polytechnic in collaboration with MTs Baitul Mubarak Partners, namely the provision and rejuvenation of educational facilities in the form of 36 tables, 76 chairs, 3 whiteboards and 3 sets of doors. This activity aims to foster the spirit of mutual cooperation and social concern. In addition, students can also hone their skills and apply knowledge to the Woodworking Practice course they get during the lecture process, namely to produce wood-based materials, using tools in the Polnep Civil Engineering Workshop. The biggest impact was felt by partners, which was the provision of new learning facilities, which were expected to be based on comfort and safety, during the teaching and learning process. The limited funds budgeted by the Center for Research and Service to the Pontianak State Polytechnic in 2025 make the rejuvenation and provision of facilities not occur optimally. One of the things that has not been handled is the provision of ceilings in classrooms. This is a challenge in the future and can also be an alternative to the next activities in the 2026 fiscal year program or other years.

REFERENCES

- Arifin, M., Nurhidayat, A., & Pratama, R. (2025). *Improving students' adaptability through community service activities*. *Journal of Nusantara Service*, 5(1), 44–52.
- Dewi, S., & Mahendra, I. (2024). *Strengthening student portfolios through involvement in community service programs*. *Journal of Vocational Education*, 12(2), 155–164.
- Ministry of National Education. (2004). *Guidelines for the provision of educational facilities*. Department of National Education.
- Hidayat, T. (2022). *The role of community service in increasing students' social awareness*. *Journal of Social Humanities*, 9(3), 210–219.
- Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia. (2019). *Decree of the Minister of Religion Number 184 of 2019 concerning the PAI Curriculum and Arabic Language*.
- Ministry of National Education of the Republic of Indonesia. (2007). *Regulation of the Minister of National Education Number 24 of 2007 concerning Standards of Facilities and Infrastructure of Junior High School/MTs*.
- Kusumawati, D. (2020). *Implementation of the tridharma of higher education in community service activities*. *Journal of Community Development*, 8(1), 11–20.
- MTs Baitul Mubarak. (2025). *Profile of MTs Baitul Mubarak*. Data and Information Technology Center of the Ministry of Education.
- Nurhayati, L., & Lubis, H. (2021). *Development of student professional ethics through community service programs*. *Journal of Character Education*, 6(2), 98–110.
- Pontianak State Polytechnic. (2025). *Profile of the Pontianak State Polytechnic*. Polnep Press.
- Polnep Research and Community Service Center. (2023). *Guidelines for the implementation of PKM activities of the Pontianak State Polytechnic*.
- Sari, R., Widodo, A., & Putri, L. (2024). *Project-based learning strategies through community service to improve students' professional competencies*. *Journal of Technology Education*, 7(1), 33–45.
- Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System.
- Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 55 of 2007 concerning Religious Education and Religious Education.
- Wulandari, A., & Prasetyo, B. (2023). *Development of students' soft skills through community service activities*. *Journal of Education and Empowerment*, 4(2), 120–129.